

Supplementary Data

Experimental protocols and additional results

Antimycobacterial pyridine carboxamides: from design to in vivo activity

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CODE GUIDE FOR FINAL COMPOUNDS

Pyridine acid	AP	6-Cl AP	PAS	PABA
Isonicotinic acid	1a	1b	1c	
2-Picolinic acid *	2a	2b	2c	2d
4-Methoxypyridine-2-carboxylic acid*	3a	3b	3c	
2-Methylpyridine-4-carboxylic acid	4a	4b	4c	
6-Chloro-pyridine-3-carboxylic acid	5a	5b	5c	5d
6-Chloro-pyridine-2-carboxylic acid	6a		6c	6d
5-Trifluoromethyl-pyridin-2-carboxylic acid	7a	7b	7c	7d
2-Hydroxy-6-methylpyridine-4-carboxylic acid			8c	
2-Chloro-6-methylpyridine-4-carboxylic acid	9a		9c	
Quinaldic acid*	10a	10b	10c/10c'	10d

*Corresponding amides were also prepared. AP – aminopyrazine, 6-Cl AP – 6-chloropyrazin-2-amine, PAS – *p*-aminosalicylic acid, PABA – *p*-aminobenzoic acid

IN VITRO ACTIVITY AND TOXICITY

1. *In vitro* antimycobacterial activity evaluation

1.1. Drug sensitive strains

Mycobacterium tuberculosis H37Rv, *M. kansasii*, *M. avium* – METHOD 1

Testing was performed according to the previously published method [1]. Tested strains *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* H37Rv CNCTC My 331/88 (ATCC 27294), *M. kansasii* CNCTC My 235/80 (ATCC 12478), and *M. avium* ssp. *avium* CNCTC My 80/72 (ATCC 15769) were obtained from the Czech National Collection of Type Cultures (CNCTC), National Institute of Public Health (Prague, Czech Republic). Middlebrook 7H9 broth of declared pH = 6.6 (Sigma-Aldrich) enriched with 0.4% of glycerol (Sigma-Aldrich) and 10% of OADC growth supplement (oleic acid, albumin, dextrose, catalase; Himedia, Mumbai, India) was used for cultivation. The tested compounds were dissolved and diluted in DMSO and mixed with broth (25 μ L of DMSO solution in 4.475 mL of broth) and then placed (100 μ L) into microplate wells. Mycobacterial inocula were suspended in isotonic saline solution and the density was adjusted to 0.5–1.0 according to the McFarland scale. These suspensions were diluted by 10^{-1} and used to inoculate the testing wells, by adding 100 μ L of mycobacterial suspension per well. The final concentrations of tested compounds in wells were 100, 50, 25, 12.5, 6.25, 3.13, and 1.56 μ g/mL. INH was used as a positive control (inhibition of growth). The negative control (visible growth) consisted of broth plus mycobacterial suspension plus DMSO. A total of 30 μ L of Alamar Blue working solution (1:1 mixture of 0.01% resazurin sodium salt (aq. sol.) and 10% Tween 80) was added after five days of incubation. Results were determined after 24 h of incubation. The MIC (in μ g/mL) was determined as the lowest concentration that prevented the blue-to-pink colour change. The MIC values of INH were 6.25–12.5 μ g/mL against *M. avium*, 3.13–12.5 μ g/mL against *M. kansasii*, and 0.1–0.2 μ g/mL against *M. tuberculosis* H37Rv. All experiments were conducted in duplicates.

Mycobacterium tuberculosis H37Ra, *M. smegmatis*, *M. aurum* – METHOD 2

The initial antimycobacterial assay was performed with fast-growing *Mycobacterium smegmatis* DSM 43465 (ATCC 607), *Mycobacterium aurum* DSM 43999 (ATCC 23366) from German Collection of Microorganisms and Cell Cultures (Braunschweig, Germany) and with the avirulent strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* H37Ra ITM-M006710 (ATCC 9431) from Belgian Coordinated Collections of Microorganisms (Antwerp, Belgium) also according to the method published in [1]. The technique used for activity determination was microdilution broth panel method using 96-well microtiter plates. The

cultivation medium was Middlebrook 7H9 broth (Sigma-Aldrich, Steinheim, Germany) enriched with 0.4% of glycerol (Sigma-Aldrich, Steinheim, Germany) and 10% of Middlebrook OADC growth supplement (Himedia, Mumbai, India). Mycobacterial strains were cultured on Middlebrook 7H9 agar and suspensions were prepared in Middlebrook 7H9 broth. The final density was adjusted to value 1.0 according to McFarland scale and diluted in a ratio 1:20 (for fast-growing mycobacteria) or 1:10 (for *M. tuberculosis*) with broth. Tested compounds were dissolved in DMSO (Sigma-Aldrich, Steinheim, Germany) then Middlebrook broth was added to obtain a concentration of 2000 µg/mL. Standards used for activity determination were isoniazid (INH), rifampicin (RIF) and ciprofloxacin (CIP) (Sigma-Aldrich, Steinheim, Germany). Final concentrations were reached by binary dilution and addition of mycobacterial suspension and were set as 500, 250, 125, 62.5, 31.25, 15.625, 7.81 and 3.91 µg/mL. Isoniazid was diluted in the range of 500–3.91 µg/mL for screening against fast-growing mycobacteria and in the range of 1–0.0078 µg/mL for screening against *M. tuberculosis*. Rifampicin final concentrations ranged from 50 to 0.39 µg/mL for fast-growing mycobacteria and from 1 to 0.0078 µg/mL for *M. tuberculosis*. Ciprofloxacin was used in the final concentrations 1–0.0078 µg/mL. The final concentration of DMSO did not exceed 2.5% (v/v) and did not affect the growth of *M. smegmatis*, *M. aurum* or *M. tuberculosis*. Positive (broth, DMSO, bacteria) and negative (broth, DMSO) growth controls were included. Plates were sealed with polyester adhesive film and incubated in the dark at 37 °C without agitation. The 0.01% solution of resazurin sodium salt was added after 48 hours of incubation for *M. smegmatis*, after 72 hours of incubation for *M. aurum* and after 120 hours of incubation for *M. tuberculosis*, respectively. After the addition of the dye, the microtitration plates were further incubated for 2.5 hours for *M. smegmatis*, 4 hours for *M. aurum* and 18 hours for *M. tuberculosis* before the activity was determined. Antimycobacterial activity was expressed as minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) and the value was read based on stain colour change (blue colour – inhibition of growth; pink colour – growth). All experiments were conducted in duplicate.

1.2. Multidrug-resistant (MDR) strains

Compound **10c** and its lactone prodrug **10c'** were evaluated against two MDR-TB strains with different resistance patterns as shown in Table S1 below. Testing against 7357/1998, 234/2005, 8666/2010, 9449/2007, Praha 1, Praha 4, and Praha 131 strains was performed according to the procedure mentioned in [2], while testing against Mtb IZAK and Mtb MATI strains was carried out according to the procedure denoted as METHOD 1 in section 1.1 above. All strains were resistant to INH, RIF, rifabutin, and streptomycin (STM); an additional resistance was present in some cases: 234/2005 resistant additionally to EMB; Praha 1 resistant additionally to EMB, and clofazimine; Praha 4 to EMB, ofloxacin (OFX), and clofazimine; and Praha 131 with additional resistance to EMB, OFX, gentamicin and amikacin. The following concentrations were used: 1000, 500, 250, 125, 62.5, 32, 16, 8, 4, 2, and 1 µM.

Table S1: Resistance profile of MDR *Mtb* strains represented by MIC values in µM.

Standard	<i>Mtb</i> IZAK	<i>Mtb</i> MATI
Streptomycin	4.0 R	16.0 R
Isoniazid	4.0 R	>8.0 R
Ethambutol	0.5 S	0.5 S
Rifampicin	>8.0 R	>8.0 R
Ciprofloxacin	0.2 S	0.2 S
Pyrazinamide	>16.0 R	128.0 R

'R' refers to resistant, while 'S' refers to sensitive.

2. *In vitro* antibacterial activity evaluation

Microdilution broth method according to The European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST) recommendations, with minor modifications, was employed for antibacterial activity evaluation *in vitro* [3]. For the screening of antibacterial activity, eight bacterial strains were included in the study, namely: *Staphylococcus aureus* subsp. *aureus* ATCC 29213 (CCM 4223); *Staphylococcus*

aureus subsp. *aureus*, methicillin-resistant, ATCC 43300 (CCM 4750); *Staphylococcus epidermidis* ATCC 12228 (CCM 4418); *Enterococcus faecalis* ATCC 29212 (CCM 4224); *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922 (CCM 3954); *Klebsiella pneumoniae* ATCC 10031 (CCM 4415); *Acinetobacter baumannii* ATCC 19606 (DSM 30007); *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ATCC 27853 (CCM 3955). Strains were purchased from the Czech Collection of Microorganisms (CCM, Brno, Czech Republic) or from the German Collection of Microorganisms and Cell Cultures (DSM, Braunschweig, Germany). The technique used for activity determination was based on a microdilution broth panel method using 96-well microtiter plates. The cultivation was done in Cation-adjusted Mueller-Hinton broth (CAMHB, M-H 2 Broth, Sigma-Aldrich), buffered to pH 7.0 at 35±2 °C. Test compounds were dissolved in DMSO to produce stock sample solutions. The final concentration of DMSO in the testing medium did not exceed 1% (v/v) of the total sample solution composition. Positive growth controls (microbes without exposure to tested compound in cultivation medium), negative growth controls (cultivation medium only), and the internal quality standards, gentamicin (GNT) and ciprofloxacin (CIP) were included in assays. Antibacterial activity was evaluated after 24 and 48 h of static incubation at 35±2 °C by visual inspection and expressed as minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC). See Table S2 for standards.

Table S2: MIC values of standards used in antibacterial activity evaluation assay expressed in µM.

standard	SA	MRSA	SE	EF	EC	KP	ACI	PA	
	48h	72h	120h						
CIP	0.256	0.128	0.128	0.512	0.008	0.008	0.512	-	0.512
GNT	1	1	0.125	>8	1	0.5	4	-	0.5

3. *In vitro* antifungal activity evaluation

Microdilution broth method according to EUCAST recommendations, with slight modifications, was employed for antifungal activity screening *in vitro* [4, 5]. Four yeast reference strains, *Candida albicans* ATCC 24433 (CCM 8320); *Candida krusei* ATCC 6258 (CCM 8271); *Candida parapsilosis* ATCC 22019 (CCM 8260); *Candida tropicalis* ATCC 750 (CCM 8264), and four filamentous fungi, *Aspergillus fumigatus* ATCC 204305; *Aspergillus flavus* CCM 8363; *Lichtheimia corymbifera* CCM 8077; and *Trichophyton interdigitale* ATCC 9533 (CCM 8377), purchased from the Czech Collection of Microorganisms (CCM, Brno, Czech Republic) or from the American Type Collection Cultures (ATCC, Manassas, VA, USA), were included in antifungal activity evaluation *in vitro*. The technique used for activity determination was based on a microdilution broth panel method with 96-well microtiter plates. The cultivation was done in RPMI-1640 medium, with glutamine and 2% glucose, buffered to pH 7.0 with MOPS (3-morpholinopropane-1-sulfonic acid). Test compounds were dissolved in DMSO to produce stock sample solutions. The final concentration of DMSO in the testing medium did not exceed 1% (v/v) of the total sample solution composition. Positive growth controls (microbes without exposure to tested compound in cultivation medium), negative growth controls (cultivation medium only), and the internal quality standards, amphotericin B (AmB) and voriconazole (VRC), were included in assays. Static incubation was performed in the dark and in a humid atmosphere, at 35±2 °C, for 24 and 48 h (72 and 120 h for *Trichophyton interdigitale*, respectively). The antifungal activity of compounds was evaluated after visual inspection and expressed as MIC, reported in µM, see Table S3 for standards.

Table S3: MIC values of standards used in antifungal activity evaluation assay expressed in µM.

Code	CA	CK	CP	CT	AF	Afla	LC	TI
	48h	48h	48h	48h	48h	48h	48h	120h
AmB	1	1	1	1	4	4	4	8
VRC	>16	16	>16	>16	1	2	>16	>16

4. *In vitro* cytotoxicity evaluation

The human hepatocellular liver carcinoma cell line HepG2, purchased from Health Protection Agency Culture Collections (ECACC, Salisbury, UK), was cultured in MEM (Minimum Essentials Eagle Medium, Sigma–Aldrich) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (PAA Laboratories, Pasching, Austria), 1% L-glutamine solution (Sigma–Aldrich) and non-essential amino acid solution (Sigma–Aldrich). Cell culture was grown in a humidified atmosphere containing 5% CO₂ at 37 °C. For subculturing, the cells were harvested after trypsin/EDTA (Sigma–Aldrich) treatment at 37 °C. To evaluate cytotoxicity, the cells treated with the tested substances were used as experimental groups, whereas untreated HepG2 cells served as controls. The cells were seeded in a density of 10,000 cells per well in a 96-well plate. The next day, the cells were treated with each of the tested substances dissolved in DMSO. The tested substances were prepared at different incubation concentrations in triplicates according to their solubility. Simultaneously, the controls representing 100% cell viability, 0% cell viability (the cells treated with 10% DMSO), no cell control and vehiculum controls were also prepared in triplicates. After 24 h incubation in a humidified atmosphere containing 5% CO₂ at 37%, the reagent from the kit CellTiter 96 Aqueous One Solution Cell Proliferation Assay (CellTiter 96; PROMEGA, Fitchburg, USA) was added. After 2 hours of incubation at 37 °C, the absorbance of samples was recorded at 490 nm (TECAN, Infinita M200, Austria). A standard toxicological parameter IC₅₀ was calculated by nonlinear regression from a semilogarithmic plot of incubation concentration versus the percentage of absorbance relative to untreated controls using GraphPad Prism 9 software.

IN VIVO TOXICITY AND EFFICACY

5. *In vivo* toxicity evaluation using *Galleria mellonella* animal model

Galleria mellonella animals have been reared in the laboratory of the Department of Biological and Medical Sciences (group of Microbiology and Immunology) at the Faculty of Pharmacy in Hradec Králové, Charles University. The larvae were fed with the artificial diet by Haydak *et al.* [6] and reared in the dark at 30 °C. Only fully vital, cream-coloured larvae at a weight range of 250–300 mg were selected for test compound administration before each experiment. In brief, the test compound was dissolved in DMSO and diluted to the required working concentration with phosphate-buffer saline, pH 7.4 (Merk, Germany), where the final concentration of DMSO corresponded to 30% (v/v). Samples were administered into larvae in a total volume 10 µl per larva in two different ways, into hemocoel through the last left proleg or by the feeding route (force-feeding method) using a Hamilton syringe. Two control groups (untreated control, buffer-injected control) were included, as well. For the intrahemocoelic administration, eight fully vital larvae, and for force-feeding method, six fully vital larvae were included in each group. The inoculated larvae and control groups were then incubated in Petri dishes at 37 °C, and mortality was monitored for five days every 24-hour interval. Death was defined as complete loss of mobility, including after a physical stimulus using a plastic pipette. The mortality (%) for each dose/time interval was calculated [6]. See Tables S4 and S5 for results.

Table S4: *In vivo* toxicity in *Galleria mellonella* model after intrahemocoelic administration of compound 10c

	Dose corresponding to mean weight of larvae per group (mg/kg of body weight)												Control group (10 µL of PBS with 30% (v/v) DMSO)	Control group (no administration)		
	Group 1		Group 2		Group 3		Group 4		Group 5		Group 6					
	1054.80		542.30		331.86		172.80		57.42		5.87					
Time (hrs)	Number of surviving larvae	Mortality (%)	Number of surviving larvae	Mortality (%)	Number of surviving larvae	Mortality (%)	Number of surviving larvae	Mortality (%)	Number of surviving larvae	Mortality (%)	Number of surviving larvae	Mortality (%)	Number of surviving larvae	Mortality (%)	Number of surviving larvae	Mortality (%)
0	8	0	8	0	8	0	8	0	8	0	8	0	4	0	4	0
24	6	25	8	0	8	0	8	0	6*	0	8	0	4	0	4	0
48	6	25	8	0	8	0	8	0	6	0	8	0	4	0	4	0
72	6	25	7	12.5	8	0	8	0	6	0	8	0	4	0	4	0
96	5	37.5	7	12.5	8	0	8	0	6	0	8	0	4	0	4	0
120	4	50	7	12.5	8	0	7	12.5	6	0	7	12.5	4	0	4	0

*Two deaths due to cannibalism

Table S5: *In vivo* toxicity in *Galleria mellonella* model after per oral administration of compound **10c**

	Dose corresponding to mean weight of larvae per group (mg/kg of body weight)												Control group (10 µL of PBS with 30% (v/v) DMSO)		Control group (no administration)					
	Group 1		Group 2		Group 3		Group 4		Group 5		Group 6									
	819.18		384.03		292.30		148.61		39.48		4.47									
Time (hrs)	Number of surviving larvae		Mortality (%)		Number of surviving larvae		Mortality (%)		Number of surviving larvae		Mortality (%)		Number of surviving larvae		Mortality (%)		Number of surviving larvae		Mortality (%)	
0	6	0	6	0	6	0	6	0	6	0	6	0	6	0	6	0	6	0	6	0
24	6	0	6	0	6	0	5	16.67	6	0	6	0	6	0	6	0	6	0	6	0
48	5	16.67	6	0	6	0	5	16.67	6	0	6	0	6	0	6	0	6	0	6	0
72	5	16.6	6	0	6	0	5	16.67	6	0	6	0	6	0	6	0	6	0	6	0
96	5	16.67	6	0	6	0	5	16.67	6	0	6	0	6	0	6	0	6	0	6	0
120	5	16.67	6	0	6	0	5	16.67	6	0	6	0	6	0	6	0	6	0	6	0

6. *In vivo* antimycobacterial activity evaluation in a murine model of TB

Female BALB/c mice (Masaryk University, Brno, Czech Republic) 4–6 weeks old were housed at five animals per cage in HEPA-filtered racks (Tecniplast, Buguggiate, Italy) in certified animal biosafety level three (BSL-3) laboratories. The mice were rested for 28 days before infection with *M. tuberculosis*. All experiments were performed according to Czech law No. 246/1992 Sb. Stock cultures of *M. tuberculosis* H37Rv (HPA cultures, Porton Down, Salisbury, Wiltshire, United Kingdom), ATCC 27294 (approx. 1×10^7 CFU/mL), enumerated by colony counting (CFU – colony forming units) on Löwenstein-Jensen agar plates (LabMediaServis, Jaroměř, Czech Republic), stored at -196°C and filled up into 150 µL aliquots.

The mice were anaesthetized with an intraperitoneal injection of xylazine 80 mg/kg (XYLAPAN, 20 mg/mL, Vétroquinol, Nymburk, Czech Republic) and ketamine 8 mg/kg (Narkamon, 50 mg/mL, Bioveta, Ivanovice na Hané, Czech Republic) and infected with *M. tuberculosis* H37Rv intranasally using 10^3 CFU/mL suspension at a volume of 50 µL per mouse. At four weeks after infection, the drug therapy was initiated in selected groups of mice. The compounds were freshly dissolved in deionized water to the concentration of 5 mg/mL and dosed (200 µL) by a gastric feeding tube once a day (50 mg/kg, five days per week, 5/7) over the course of four weeks. The positive control of the treatment was isoniazid (25 mg/kg, 5/7). The dosing was calculated for an idealized mouse of 20 g weight. The experiment also contained the control groups to verify the success of the infection and its development in untreated mice.

Four weeks after infection, the mice were sacrificed by carbon dioxide inhalation. After euthanasia, organs (lungs and spleens) were aseptically removed and homogenized in tea strainers with sterile saline.

Diluted samples of both organs were incubated on Löwenstein–Jensen agar plates at 35.5 °C for two to three weeks. The formed colonies of *M. tuberculosis* were counted, and the value of CFU was calculated. During the experiment, any visual signs of infection or death were registered.

IN VITRO DETERMINATION OF MECHANISM OF ACTION

7. Susceptibility testing of *Mtb* H37Ra strains overproducing enzymes of the folate pathway

The strains *Mtb* H37Ra overproducing dihydrofolate synthase FolP1, dihydrofolate reductases DfrA or RibD, and dihydropteroate synthase FolC were constructed as described: Standard PCR strategy was used to amplify genes corresponding to folP1 (rv3608c), dfrA (rv2763c) or ribD (rv2671), *folC* (rv2447c) from *Mtb* H37Rv [the primers were FolP1-F (5'-CGTGCCATATGGTGAGTCCGGCGCCCGTG-3'), FolP1-R (5'-CGTGCAAGCTTTCAGCCATCGCGTTCTATCCT-3'), DfrA-F (5'-GTGGCATATGATGGTGGGCTGATCTGGGC-3'), DfrA-R (5'-GTGGAAGCTTTCATGAGCGGTGGTAGCTGTA-3'), RibD-F (5-AGAGACATATGATGCCCCGACTCTGGTCAG-3'), RibD-R (5-AGAGAAAGCTTTCAGGTCTTGACGTAGCGG-3'), FolC-F (5'-ATAGACCATATGAATTCGACGAATTCGGGCC-3') and FolC-R (5'-TATCATAAGCTTTCATTGCGGATCACGACCGAAC-3')] which introduces sequences for restriction endonucleases *Nde*I or *Hind*III (underlined). The genes were cloned to pV2 expression vector allowing expression of recombinant protein with N-terminal His₆ tag fusion [7] and the resulting construct was electroporated to *Mtb* H37Ra cells. The production of recombinants was confirmed by immunoblot with anti-His antibodies.

Overproducing strains, as well as control strain *Mtb* H37Ra pV2 carrying empty vector, were grown in Middlebrook 7H9 broth (Difco) supplemented with albumin-dextrose-catalase, 0.05% Tween 80 and 20 µg/mL kanamycin in 100 µL aliquots in 96-well plates in the presence of different concentrations of compound **10c**, its sodium salt (**10cNa**) or PAS. After 11 days of incubation at 37 °C, 30 mL of resazurin in final concentration 0.01% (w/v) was added and after 24 h the growth was evaluated based on the colour of the culture. The minimal inhibitory concentration (MIC) was defined as the lowest compound concentration that prevented the change in colour from blue to pink (reduction of resazurin to resorufin).

8. ¹⁴C metabolic labelling and lipid analysis

The cells of *M. tuberculosis* H37Rv were cultivated in 7H9 broth with 10% albumin-dextrose-catalase and 0.05% Tween 80 at 37 °C with shaking (120 rpm). When O.D. (600 nm) of the culture reached 0.16, the compound **10c**, or its sodium salt **10cNa** (both dissolved in DMSO) were added in final concentrations 0, 1.5, 3 and 6 µg/mL. The final concentration of DMSO was kept at 2 %. PAS was used as a control drug in a final concentration 0.5 µg/mL. After 24 h of static cultivation at 37 °C ¹⁴C-acetate (specific activity 110 mCi/mmol, ARC) was added in final concentration 0.5 mCi/mL and after the next 24 h the cultures were harvested. The lipids were extracted from whole cells from 100 mL cultures with 1.5 mL chloroform/methanol (1:2, v/v) at 56 °C for 1 h followed by the extraction with 1.5 mL chloroform/methanol (2:1, v/v) at 56 °C for 1.5 h. The organic extracts were combined, dried under N₂, and subjected to biphasic Folch washing [8]. Dried extracts were dissolved in 50 mL of chloroform/methanol (2:1, v/v) and 10 mL were loaded on TLC silica gel 60 F₂₅₄ plates (Merck). Lipids were separated in Solvent I [chloroform/methanol/water (20:4:0.5, v/v/v)], Solvent II [chloroform/methanol/ammonium hydroxide/water (65:25:0.5:4, v/v/v/v)], or Solvent III [petroleum ether (60–80°C)/ethyl acetate (98:2, v/v, 3 runs)], and visualized by Amersham™ Typhoon™ Biomolecular Imager. Alternatively, the fatty acids were extracted from whole cells from 100 mL cultures and derivatized to corresponding methyl esters [9]. Dried extracts were dissolved in 50 mL of

chloroform/methanol (2:1, v/v), 10 mL were loaded on TLC silica gel 60 F₂₅₄ plates (Merck), and methyl esters of fatty acids were separated in Solvent IV [*n*-hexane/ethyl acetate (95:5, v/v, 3 runs)]. Alternatively, before loading the samples, the TLC plates were impregnated with 5% AgNO₃. The profiles of ¹⁴C labelled molecules were visualized as described above.

9. Methionine supplementation assay

The *M. tuberculosis* H37Ra cells were grown in 7H9 broth supplemented with 10% albumin-dextrose-catalase and 0.05% Tween 80 in the presence of 8 or 16 µg/mL of **10c**, **10cNa** or 0.8 µg/mL of PAS, and in the presence of 0, 50, 100, 250 and 500 µM methionine. Plates were incubated at 37 °C for 15 days, and the growth was evaluated by measuring the values of O.D. (600 nm).

PHARMACOKINETICS AND METABOLISM

10. *In vitro* metabolism in human liver microsomes

The HPLC system used in this study was Dionex Ultimate 3000 UHPLC RS consisting of RS Pump, RS Column Compartment, RS Autosampler and Diode Array Detector controlled by Chromeleon (version 7.2.9. build 11323) software (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Germering, Germany) connected to Q Exactive Plus Orbitrap mass spectrometer with Thermo Xcalibur (version 3.1.66.10.) software (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Bremen, Germany). Detection was performed by mass spectrometry in positive mode. Settings of the heated electrospray source were: spray voltage 3.5 kV; capillary temperature 220 °C; sheath gas 55 arbitrary units; auxiliary gas 15 arbitrary units; spare gas 3 arbitrary units; probe heater temperature 220 °C; max spray current 100 mA and S-lens RF Level 50. Solvents and other common chemicals were purchased from VWR (Stribrna Skalice, Czech Republic). Solvents for chromatographic procedures were supplied in LC-MS grade. An internal standard [2-hydroxy-4-(quinoline-3-carboxamido)benzoic acid] was synthesized by us and used during the experiment.

Sample preparation

The ammonium salt of compound 10c and its lactone form 10c` were incubated with Human Liver Microsomes according to the microsomal stability assay protocol available from [10]. Briefly, the tested compounds were dissolved in DMSO to produce stock sample solutions. The final concentration of DMSO in the incubation mixture did not exceed 1% (v/v) and the concentration of tested compounds was set at 3 µM. 12.5 µL of pooled Human Liver Microsomes (concentration 0.5 mg/mL, H2620, LOT no. 1210347, SekiSui, XenoTech, Canada) was mixed with 5 µL of 3 µM stock solution and 458 µL of 0.1M potassium phosphate buffer solution (pH = 7.4, adjusted by addition of NaOH) and preincubated for 5 min (300 rpm, 25 °C). The biotransformation reaction was started by addition of 25 µL of RapidStart NADPH Regenerating System (K5000, LOT. 1910008, SekiSui, XenoTech, Canada) and then incubated for 5 different time points (0, 5, 15, 30, 45 min). The reaction was terminated by the addition of 500 µL of cooled acetonitrile (-20 °C) with 1 µM internal standard [2-hydroxy-4-(quinoline-3-carboxamido)benzoic acid] and centrifuged for 5 min (14 000 rpm, 20 °C). Subsequently, 400 µL of supernatant was transferred to the vial and analyzed. Three types of blank samples were prepared in the same way, with a one-step exception. In the biological blank sample 5 µL of DMSO was added instead of 5 µL stock solution; 50 µL of water instead of HLM was added in the chemical blanks, and in the case of the control blank sample 25 µL of water was added instead of 25 µL of RapidStart System.

HPLC-MS analysis

The supernatants were measured by the HPLC-MS system mentioned above. Results were obtained by the reverse phase gradient elution method of 7.5 min on the C18 column (Kinetex EVO, 2.1 x 50 mm, 1.7 µm, Phenomenex, Torrance, California, USA). The mobile phase A was ultrapure ASTM I type water

(resistance 18.2 M Ω cm at 25 °C) prepared by Barnstead Smart2Pure 3 UV/UF apparatus (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Bremen, Germany) with 0.1% (v/v) formic acid; mobile phase B was acetonitrile with 0.1% (v/v) of formic acid. The flow was constant at 0.5 ml/min. The method started with 0.3 min of isocratic flow of 5% B, the concentration of B was then increased to 100% in 3.3 min and remained constant at 100% B for 0.7 min. The composition then reverted to 5% B and was equilibrated for 3.5 min. The column was tempered to 27 °C and the injection volume was 5 μ l. The areas of the compounds (A_{cmp}) and internal standards (A_{IS}) were detected in extracted ion chromatograms from the mass spectrometer data in positive mode. The ratio of $A_{\text{cmp}}/A_{\text{IS}}$ was calculated and normalized to the value in time 0 min (Table S6). The remaining percentage of the compound was logarithmized and plotted against the time of incubation (Figure S1). The $t_{1/2}$ value, and CL_{int} were calculated according to the Cyprotex protocol [10]. The elimination rate constant (k) is the absolute value of the slope of the linear regression. The half-life $t_{1/2} = \ln 2/k$. The intrinsic clearance is calculated as $CL_{\text{int}} = (V \ln 2)/t_{1/2}$, where V = incubation volume (μ L) / mass of the protein in incubation (mg). The calculated half-life and intrinsic clearance are reported in Table S7.

Table S6: Raw data of stability assessment of compounds 10c' and 10c incubated with human microsomes.

Compound 10c'	Area (A_{cmp})	Area IS (A_{IS})	ratio (A_{cmp}/A_{IS})	remaining compound (%)	ln (remaining percent)
0 min incubation_1	34359067	32758216	1.049	100.00	4.605
0 min incubation_2	30128556	27950575	1.078	100.00	4.605
0 min incubation_3	30854176	26450342	1,166	100,00	4.605
5 min incubation_1	24655806	28026545	0,880	80.14	4.384
5 min incubation_2	24907405	30079561	0,828	75.43	4.323
5 min incubation_3	22971855	28247783	0,813	74.08	4.305
15 min incubation_1	9217802	30966312	0,298	27,12	3.300
15 min incubation_2	10759134	30124333	0,357	32.54	3.482
15 min incubation_3	9515730	30622874	0,311	28.30	3.343
30 min incubation_1	4144440	27748979	0,149	13.61	2.610
30 min incubation_2	4020781	28038364	0,143	13,06	2.570
30 min incubation_3	4678705	34137986	0,137	12,48	2.525
45 min incubation_1	2249544	28157588	0,080	7,28	1.985
45 min incubation_2	2391010	31829141	0,075	6,84	1.923
45 min incubation_3	1963604	28489567	0,069	6,28	1.837
Compound 10c	Area (A_{cmp})	Area IS (A_{IS})	ratio (A_{cmp}/A_{IS})	remaining compound (%)	ln (remaining percent)
0 min incubation_1	112511061	22108067	5,089	100.00	4.605
0 min incubation_2	123840247	23781055	5,208	100.00	4.606
0 min incubation_3	120303150	23591368	5,099	100.00	4.607
5 min incubation_1	142288787	29260327	4,863	94.75	4,551
5 min incubation_2	146955332	28408780	5,173	100,80	4,613
5 min incubation_3	138000517	27737647	4,975	96,94	4,574
15 min incubation_1	138729773	29376946	4,722	92,02	4,522
15 min incubation_2	146581303	27710769	5,290	103,07	4,635
15 min incubation_3	139728524	28952145	4,826	94,04	4,544
30 min incubation_1	135964062	28159371	4,828	94,08	4,544
30 min incubation_2	143416489	31339919	4,576	89,17	4,491
30 min incubation_3	143973309	32279490	4,460	86,91	4,465
45 min incubation_1	151283873	30752402	4,919	95,86	4,563
45 min incubation_2	134653866	26956685	4,995	97,33	4,578
45 min incubation_3	130757227	26385863	4,956	96,56	4,570

A_{cmp} – peak area of the compound, A_{IS} – peak area of the internal standard

Figure S1: Analysis of incubation of compound 10c' (lactone) with HLM (15 min incubation_2).

Table S7: Calculated values of $t_{1/2}$ and CL_{int} .

	Cmpd 10c	cmpd 10c'	diazepam	verapamil
$t_{1/2}$ (min)	630	11	990	18
CL_{int} ($\mu\text{l}/\text{min}/\text{mg}$ of protein)	2.2	122.3	1.4	76.4

11. Phase I metabolites identification

The methodology for the identification of phase I metabolites was inspired by Nepovímová *et al* [11]. The tested compounds were prepared as mentioned in the previous chapter but the final concentration of the mixture was established at 90 μM . Briefly, 25 μl of pooled Human Liver Microsomes (concentration 0.5 mg/mL, H2620, LOT no. 1210347, SekiSui, XenoTech, Canada) was mixed with 5 μl of 90 μM stock solution and 420 μl of 0.1M potassium phosphate buffer solution (pH = 7.4, adjusted by addition of NaOH) and preincubated for 5 min (300 rpm, 25°C). The biotransformation reaction was started with the addition of 25 μl of RapidStart NADPH Regenerating System (K5000, LOT. 1910008, SekiSui, XenoTech, Canada) and then incubated for 3 hours. The reaction was terminated by addition of 500 μl of cooled acetonitrile (-20 °C) and centrifuged for 5 min (14 000 rpm, 20°C). After that, 800 μl of the supernatant were evaporated to dryness and stored in a freezer (-80 °C). Prior to analysis, all samples were thawed at laboratory temperature and then reconstituted in 100 μl of 50% acetonitrile in water (v/v). The three types of blank samples were prepared as described above.

HPLC-MS analysis

The identification of phase I metabolites was obtained by the HPLC-HRMS system mentioned above. In this study, a reverse phase method was used on a C18 column (Kinetex C18, 3.0 x 150 mm, 2.6 μm , Phenomenex, Torrance, California, USA). The mobile phase was as above: water and acetonitrile with formic acid. Initially, 5% B flowed for 1 min, and then the composition increased to 100% B in 14 min. After 1 min of the constant flow of 100% B, the composition of mobile phases reverted to 5% B and equilibrated for 4 min. The total run time of the method was 20 min. The column temperature was set to 27 °C and the injection volume was 5 μl . The metabolites were determined in total ion current spectra from the mass spectrometry data obtained in positive mode. Figure S2 presents the extracted ion chromatograms from the analysis of compounds 10c and 10c' and their formed metabolites M1, M2 and M3.

Figure S2: Identification of metabolites of compound 10c and 10c' after 3 hours of incubation with HLM

IN SILICO SIMULATIONS

12. Binding of 10c to mycobacterial methionyl-tRNA synthetase (mtMetRS)

Software

In silico calculations were performed in Molecular Operating Environment (MOE) 2022.09 (Chemical Computing Group Inc., Montreal, QC, Canada) under Amber10:EHT forcefield if not otherwise stated. Figures were generated using MOE. Molecular dynamics (MD) simulation was run using NAMD (University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign, IL, USA) [12]. MD stages 1–3 were simulated using NAMD 2.14. Phases 4–6 were run using NAMD 3 alpha 9 utilizing the CUDA GPU acceleration. The trajectories were analyzed using [VMD](#) (Visual Molecular Dynamics, version 1.9.4a53, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign, IL, USA) [13] after aligning the trajectory on C α atoms of residues 1–339 (the domain containing the binding site).

Molecular docking

The ligand for docking (compound **10c**) was generated from SMILES, using the MOE built-in function to predict the dominant protonation state at pH 7. The dominant protomer (abundance of 96% at pH 7) contained deprotonated carboxylate but a non-ionized phenolic group. 3D coordinates were minimized until RMS gradient $0.01 \text{ kcal.mol}^{-1}.\text{\AA}^{-1}$. 3D coordinates of methionyl-tRNA synthetase (mtMetRS) of *M. tuberculosis* were downloaded from the PDB database (pdb id: 6ax8). The system was prepared by MOE QuickPrep functionality with default settings, which included corrections of structural errors, the addition of hydrogens, calculation of partial charges, 3D optimization of protonation/tautomeric states and *H*-bond network (Protonate3D), deletion of water molecules further than 4.5 Å from ligand or protein, and a restrained minimization (to RMS gradient of $0.01 \text{ kcal.mol}^{-1}.\text{\AA}^{-1}$) of ligand and pocket residues within 8 Å from the ligand. Subsequently, all solvent molecules were removed.

The docking was focused on the pocket, which was defined as a set of residues having at least one atom within 4.5 Å from the co-crystallized ligand. Parameters of the MOE docking protocol: **Placement:** Triangle Matcher; Score: London Dg; retain 30 poses. **Refinement stage** – Induced fit (free to move pocket residues); Score: GBVI/WSA Dg; retain 5 poses. Sampling of ligand conformations – Rotate bonds.

Molecular dynamics

The system for MD simulation was constructed from the selected docked pose (the best by docking score) of compound **10c**. Input for the MD simulation was prepared in MOE, applying the parameters from Amber10:EHT forcefield. The system was solvated using TIP3P waters in a 10 Å margin periodic boundaries box, neutralized, and buffered using NaCl ($c = 0.15\text{M}$). In the simulation, non-bonded Van der Waals interactions were truncated (switching distance 10, cutoff distance 12). Long-range electrostatics were treated using the Particle Mesh Ewald (PME). Bonds to hydrogen atoms were constrained using the ShakeH algorithm (with the default convergence criterion of $1.0\text{e-}8$). The temperature was controlled by Langevin dynamics, and the pressure was treated using Nosé–Hoover–Langevin piston pressure control, both as implemented in NAMD. The time step was set to 2 fs and the coordinates were recorded each 10 ps.

MD Protocol (temperature T in kelvins, pressure P in bar, r is a restrain to heavy atoms as defined in MOE, see below*).

1. Restrained minimization { ps=10 T=0 r=0.5 };
2. Unrestrained minimization { ps=10 T=0 };
3. Heating with gradually released restraints { ps=180 T=(10,300) r=(0.5,10) };
4. NVT equilibration { ps=200 T=300 };
5. NPT equilibration { ps=1600 T=300 P=1 };
6. NPT production { ps=80000 T=300 P=1 };

* Restraint: Heavy atom tether restraint in Å. A value of 0 means that heavy atoms are fixed, while *e.g.* 1 means that a restraint force constant that produces a 1 Å radial standard deviation from the reference position will be applied. If no restraint gradient is defined, this is a constant restraint applied during the entire MD segment.

Production runs of 80 ns were performed in 3 independent replicas, starting from the equilibrated structure after Stage 5.

Figure S3. RMSD of Ca atoms of the binding site domain (residues 1–339) during the 80ns MD simulation of the 10c-mtMetRS complex

Figure S4. RMSD of ligand atoms (without hydrogens) during the 80ns MD simulation of the 10c-mtMetRS complex

OTHER

13. SMILES of final compounds

Code	SMILES
1a	<chem>O=C(NC1=NC=CN=C1)C2=CC=NC=C2</chem>
2a	<chem>O=C(NC1=NC=CN=C1)C2=NC=CC=C2</chem>
3a	<chem>O=C(NC1=NC=CN=C1)C2=NC=CC(OC)=C2</chem>
4a	<chem>O=C(NC1=NC=CN=C1)C2=CC=NC(C)=C2</chem>
5a	<chem>O=C(NC1=NC=CN=C1)C2=CN=C(Cl)C=C2</chem>
6a	<chem>O=C(NC1=NC=CN=C1)C2=NC(Cl)=CC=C2</chem>
7a	<chem>O=C(NC1=NC=CN=C1)C2=NC=C(C(F)(F)F)C=C2</chem>
9a	<chem>O=C(NC1=NC=CN=C1)C2=CC(C)=NC(Cl)=C2</chem>
10a	<chem>O=C(C1=NC2=CC=CC=C2C=C1)NC3=NC=CN=C3</chem>
1b	<chem>O=C(NC1=NC(Cl)=CN=C1)C2=CN=CC=C2</chem>
2b	<chem>O=C(NC1=NC(Cl)=CN=C1)C2=CC=NC=C2</chem>
3b	<chem>O=C(NC1=NC(Cl)=CN=C1)C2=NC=CC(OC)=C2</chem>
4b	<chem>O=C(NC1=NC(Cl)=CN=C1)C2=CC=NC(C)=C2</chem>
5b	<chem>O=C(NC1=NC(Cl)=CN=C1)C2=CN=C(Cl)C=C2</chem>
7b	<chem>O=C(C1=NC=C(C(F)(F)F)N=C1)NC2=NC(Cl)=CN=C2</chem>
10b	<chem>O=C(C1=NC2=CC=CC=C2C=C1)NC3=NC(Cl)=CN=C3</chem>
1c	<chem>O=C(O)C1=CC=C(NC(C2=CC=NC=C2)=O)C=C1O</chem>
2c	<chem>O=C(O)C1=CC=C(NC(C2=NC=CC=C2)=O)C=C1O</chem>
3c	<chem>O=C(O)C1=CC=C(NC(C2=NC=CC(OC)=C2)=O)C=C1O</chem>
4c	<chem>O=C(O)C1=CC=C(NC(C2=CC=NC(C)=C2)=O)C=C1O</chem>
5c	<chem>O=C(O)C1=CC=C(NC(C2=CN=C(Cl)C=C2)=O)C=C1O</chem>
6c	<chem>O=C(O)C1=CC=C(NC(C2=NC(Cl)=CC=C2)=O)C=C1O</chem>
7c	<chem>O=C(O)C1=CC=C(NC(C2=NC(C(F)(F)F)=CC=C2)=O)C=C1O</chem>
8c	<chem>O=C(O)C1=CC=C(NC(C2=CC(C)=NC(O)=C2)=O)C=C1O</chem>
9c	<chem>O=C(O)C1=CC=C(NC(C2=CC(C)=NC(Cl)=C2)=O)C=C1O</chem>
10c	<chem>O=C(O)C1=CC=C(NC(C2=NC3=CC=CC=C3C=C2)=O)C=C1O</chem>
10c'	<chem>O=C(C1=NC2=CC=CC=C2C=C1)NC3=CC=C4C(OCOC4=O)=C3</chem>
2d	<chem>O=C(O)C1=CC=C(NC(C2=NC=CC=C2)=O)C=C1</chem>
5d	<chem>O=C(O)C1=CC=C(NC(C2=CN=C(Cl)C=C2)=O)C=C1</chem>
6d	<chem>O=C(O)C1=CC=C(NC(C2=NC(Cl)=CC=C2)=O)C=C1</chem>
7d	<chem>O=C(O)C1=CC=C(NC(C2=NC(C(F)(F)F)=CC=C2)=O)C=C1</chem>
10d	<chem>O=C(O)C1=CC=C(NC(C2=NC3=CC=CC=C3C=C2)=O)C=C1</chem>

14. Representative ^1H -NMR and ^{13}C -NMR spectra of selected compounds
a) ^1H -NMR and ^{13}C -NMR spectra of compound **10a**

b) $^1\text{H-NMR}$ and $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ spectra of compound **10b**

c) H-NMR and ^{13}C -NMR spectra of compound **10c**

d) $^1\text{H-NMR}$ and $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ spectra of compound **10c'**

e) ^1H -NMR and ^{13}C -NMR spectra of compound **10d**

15. HPLC-UV records of purity for compound **10c** and its lactone **10c'**

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